

ORGANIZATION OF INTENSIVE GARDENS HIGH INCOME THE FOUNDATION OF OBTAINING

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Annotation: *this article mainly describes the importance of intensive Gardens today, the agrotechnics of garden construction. At the same time, the article also describes the advantages and disadvantages of intensive Gardens. Information is also provided on what irrigation methods are used along with the formation of intensive Gardens.*

Keywords: *intensive, garden, water, resource, drip irrigation, simbagaz, agriculture, ecology, agrotechnics, global, tree.*

Today there is a period when a huge number of environmental problems are raging in the world. Due to environmental problems, various natural problems are in full swing today, which is why it is not losing its influence on both agriculture and of course. Today, agriculture is mainly affected by problems such as global warming, increased demand for Water Resources, various damage to the crop caused by kunanda, various levels of excessive salinity of the lands, erosion of fertile soils, in addition to various problems, agriculture is affected by this, the main reason is a violation of Ecology, and environmental degradation is the excessive and inefficient use of Natural Resources On the territory of Uzbekistan, too, the yield level of some annual crop species is decreasing due to various factors, and to prevent this, it would be advisable not to occupy land with one type of crop, but to establish gardens and vines on soils with a relatively low yield. For this reason, it will also be advisable to shape new gardens albata. If we dwell on the intensive garden grid, which today has a high efficiency, then the cooling of the fruit has been completely eliminated by the use of advanced agrotechnical measures in modern intensive Gardens. The yield is also considered 1.5-1.7 times higher than that of previous intensive Gardens. Alternatively, the fruit of today's intensive Gardens is an export bop product in addition to the fact that in the conditions of Uzbekistan, such gardens become a source of net income for several years, covering the expenses spent at most in 3-5 years, have also been tried in experiments. If we dwell on the requirements for the organization of intensive gardens, it should be noted that in the land where low and desolate gardens are planted, fresh groundwater should not be close to 1.5-2 M and mineralized groundwater should not be close to 3-3.5 m. And in the land near the rivers, the groundwater level will be 1.0-1.2 m. only their soil composition should be free of harmful (chloride and sulfate) salts. The area allocated for irrigated intensive

gardens should be flat and its slope should not exceed 4-5 degrees. The fruit tree grown in simbagazy gardens should be 100 cm wide in mature trees and 150 cm in low-lying trees so that the sun illuminates the trunk well in addition to the fact that when the rows are 3.5-4.0 m between the trees their bodies will be well provided with sunlight. Every year, potassium 60-70 kg of nitrogen fertilizers are applied per hectare in the fall, with a volume of 40-50 kg of phosphorus 30-40 kg, until the fruit trees are fully harvested. In addition to different times, different types of drugs are used for the purpose of making hioia from kunanda. One of the most convenient aspects of intensive Gardens is that in this type of gardens, it is very convenient to apply modern types of irrigation, in particular drip irrigation, and allows you to achieve high efficiency. In addition, it is possible to plant pulses between the trees, which indicates additional income. Let's dwell on the advantages of creating intensive Gardens in an additional way: The fact that the yield level is high, it quickly covers the costs incurred, it is easy to apply agrotechnical work, its yield is high-quality (exportbop is a product), the length of storage of crop from gardens, the creation of workplaces when processing enterprises are built, the saving of irrigation water when modern irrigation methods are used, etc. One of the reasons why much attention has been paid to the creation of long-term Gardens in the Republic to date is the fact that it is very convenient to export the crop from deer to foreign countries. Higher yields can be achieved each year if agrotechnical work is weather - permeable in time, unlike annuals because crops from gardens and vines are perennial. Just as everything has an advantage, intensive gardens also have disadvantages that include those below: Creating intensive Gardens requires investment: Failure to give the intended yield if agratechnics are not followed; Examples include the fact that varieties brought from abroad can hit cold in winter, and in summer they suffer from various diseases, etc.

Although there are some shortcomings in the organization of intensive gardens, but the organization of intensive Gardens is considered promising plans. For this reason, crop varieties suitable for our new natural conditions are being tested on yartilib test sites by Uzbek scientists. In conclusion, foreign countries are considered to have extensive experience in creating intensive Gardens. This is another great achievement for us if we can apply it to ourselves by studying the experiences of foreign countries. For this reason, much attention is paid to improving personnel skills today. Personnel qualification increases are a pledge of future asa achievements.

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